

A NEW APPROACH TO SUCCESSFUL INCLUSIVE EDUCATION - FIVE DIMENSIONAL EDUCATION

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Preface

Ensuring that all students have equal and fair access to education and creating an environment where they can learn and grow together is very important. Many countries are working hard to achieve inclusive education, but there are still many challenges. To make inclusive education successful, we need customized educational curricula. Additionally, each country has different educational environments, and many teachers lack the necessary expertise. Moreover, many parents do not have enough information about inclusive education.

To solve these issues, we propose three solutions:

1. Implementing Five Dimensional Education as a curriculum for inclusive education.
2. Training teachers to effectively carry out this education.
3. Educating parents to support their children's learning.

Inclusive education means that every student should receive the right education, regardless of their personal circumstances. But how can we provide proper education when each student's situation is different? The key is maximizing each individual's talents. When personal happiness is connected to education, opportunities become fair, and social, cultural, and economic inequalities can be reduced.

Every person has different learning receptivity due to their unique characteristics, so it is difficult to expect the same results from everyone. However, if we help students maximize their talents, they can achieve a successful life. Education should focus on talent maximization rather than making distinctions based on disabilities, wealth, or cultural differences.

There are many examples of people overcoming disabilities and achieving success. One famous case is Stephen Hawking, a brilliant physicist. Even though he had a severe physical disability, he accepted his condition and worked to maximize his intellectual strength. As a result, he became one of the world's greatest physicists. Every person has unique talents, and by maximizing these talents, individuals can find happiness, achieve success, and contribute to

society and their country. The key to inclusive education is creating an environment where students can overcome difficulties and develop their abilities.

So, how can students with disabilities or low learning receptivity unlock and maximize their hidden talents? While governments, schools, organizations, and parents all play important roles, the most crucial factor is developing five key human elements:

1. Intellectual Power
2. Mental Power
3. Physical Power
4. Self-Management Ability
5. Human Relational Ability

If we continuously work on these areas, we can create an education system where all students receive fair learning opportunities without discrimination. This will not only improve education but also positively impact society as a whole.

What is 5-Dimensional Education?

1. The Reason Why Not Everyone Succeeds in Their Children's Education

Not all parents succeed in educating their children because they do not recognize the importance of receptivity. Even if they provide good education, children may not fully absorb or utilize it due to various factors that block their receptivity. Understanding and addressing these obstacles is crucial for educational success.

If a farmer scatters high-quality seeds onto poor or unprepared soil, the seeds will not be able to take root, grow properly, or produce healthy crops. No matter how good the seeds are, if the soil is too hard, too shallow, or filled with weeds, the plants will struggle to survive and will not yield good fruit.

Figure 1. Sowing seeds without soil preparation.

Similarly, in education, even the best teaching and knowledge will not lead to success if the learner's receptivity is not properly developed.

2. Five Reasons That Destroy Receptivity

1) Distorted Cognitive Frame

When individuals view the world through a rigid or incorrect perspective, they struggle to accept new knowledge or truth.

We tend to hear or see only what we want to hear or see. Teachers provide the same content to all students. However, while some understand the key information they need to know, others may focus only on minor details such as the teacher's examples or jokes because of the distorted intellectual frame.

Therefore, if students have a distorted intellectual framework, that is, if they are wearing intellectual colored glasses, they will not be able to distinguish between truth and falsehood, it is essential to help them correct this.

2) Weak Mental Strength

A lack of perseverance and resilience makes it difficult for individuals to endure challenges and continue learning.

The limbic system in the human brain rejects incoming information that makes our heart feel uncomfortable. Sometimes we say to ourselves, "I cannot do this," or "I just hate doing this."

When we repeatedly tell ourselves these things, our brain makes us believe it so much that we actually can not do anything. In other words, a broken spirit seldom produces a competent individual, so it is essential to help them correct this.

3) *Lack of Physical Strength*

Poor physical condition leads to low concentration and energy, making it hard to stay engaged in learning.

In Korea, we often find a few students who feel sleepy as soon as classes start in high school. There are also students who look at the teacher during class but are thinking about something else.

Thus, good teaching is ineffective if the students' bodies are not vitalized, so it is essential to help them correct this.

4) *Poor Self-Management*

Without discipline and time management, individuals become easily distracted and unable to sustain continuous learning.

If one's ability to manage time and energy properly is distorted, it ultimately hampers their potential for growth and learning, so it is essential to help them correct this.

5) *Unhealthy Human Relationships*

Negative interactions with others create emotional barriers, preventing individuals from receiving guidance, feedback, and new perspectives effectively. When students are told to study by adults they dislike, their reaction can be very negative. There are even statistics showing that if a student dislikes his or her teacher for a particular subject, their score in that subject tends to worsen.

Interpersonal relationships are a very decisive factor that determines whether a person can become truly competent or not. So it is essential to help them correct this.

Figure 2. Five areas of personality that affect perceptivity.

3. The 5 Dimensional Education

So, we need to know how to fix and heal these five broken areas so that human being can build strong receptive abilities.

For this purpose, Five-Dimensional Education was created. The Five-Dimensional Education is composed of 25 curriculums designed to transform each of the five elements.

Table 1. 25 curriculums.

Intellectual Power Ability to discern truth from falsehood	Mental Power Ability to internalize knowledge	Physical Power Ability to turn truth into action	Self-management ability Ability to distribute energy correctly	Human relation capability Ability to share energy with others
Knowledge management capability	Establishing firm sense of purpose in life	5 dimensional health management method	Expansion of free energy	Discovering unique human traits
Multilingual capability	Fostering responsiveness	Maximum output methods	Time management	Me and family
Understanding of the natural world	Nurturing rich emotional capacity	Work and rest	Financial management	Me and colleagues
Capability to understand history	Positive thinking method	Career view	Language and behavior management	Me and society
Creative intellect	Establishment of proper world view	Establishment of holistic personality	Convergence-oriented capability	The ideal global human

At that time, I also realized that these five elements are connected to the core components of human character. The elements of human character are usually seen as the following: the ability to judge right and wrong (Intellectual Power); respecting your own and others' feelings (Mental Power); taking responsibility for your actions and decisions (Physical Power); controlling and managing your emotions, actions, and habits (Self-Management Ability); understanding your responsibilities to the community (Human Relation Ability).

Therefore, I realized that Five-Dimensional Education is a holistic education that restores human character. Ultimately, it brings about changes in receptivity through changes in human nature, and can develop truly capable students.

4. Results of the Five-Dimensional Education

The 5 Dimensional Education has been implemented in over 10 countries. At Yanji No. 2 High School in China, the lowest-performing class improved to become the top class within two years.

In Mongolia, the "Bright Future School," which educates street children, adopted Five-Dimensional Education in 1998, leading to significant improvement in students' abilities. In 2001, a meeting with the President of Mongolia resulted in the establishment of Mongolia International University (MIU).

The program was also introduced to Laos National University in 2007 and Tanzania Union University in 2012.

In South Korea, the Five-Dimensional Education was applied at Seine High School, where low-performing students improved dramatically, achieving a 92% college admission rate within three years. Similarly, excellent results were achieved at Dongducheon Middle and High School. Over 15,000 teachers have been trained in Five-Dimensional Education.

In 2017, KAIST Graduate School of Future Strategy recognized it as a national future education model in the "National Future Education Strategy Report."

In 2024, in a case study from a local high school in the United States, La Mirada High School (located in La Mirada, California), the application of a 5-Dimensional Education method led to tremendous improvements. As a result, the number of students meeting the academic standards in mock state exams increased significantly—from the 3% range to the 60% range. Over time, their positive attitude toward this education method grew. The school looks forward to further development and growth among its students through holistic education.

Figure 3, 4. China. Reported in a Chinese newspaper.

Figure 5, 6, 7. Mongolia. Discussed establishing a fifth dimension university with President Bhagavandi of Mongolia.

Figure 8, 9. Korea. Miraculous things are reported in the Korean media.

Figure 10, 11. KAIST. KAIST Adopts 5-D Education as National Future.

Figure 12. United States. U.S. high school students with a 5 dimensional education see dramatic performance gains.

5. Training for parents and teachers

Why do teachers and parents need to change?

The reason our children cannot fully develop their abilities is because of issues with receptivity. But where do these issues come from? They come from the influence of people around them, who lower their receptivity.

So, who has the greatest influence on a child's receptivity? The answer is parents and teachers. Some students refuse to study because they dislike their teacher. Others struggle in their studies due to a poor relationship with their parents. If we want to raise children who succeed and thrive in this world, parents must first solve the issues that decrease their children's receptivity.

That is why in Five Dimensional education, we not only focus on educating students but also prioritize the transformation of teachers and parents. When they change, it becomes a great blessing for their children. It is not enough to simply teach good things to children. True change happens when teachers and parents also take part in this education. When they change, their children will also change and reach their full potential.

Training for teachers

Teachers play a crucial role in cultivating the characteristics of future human resources in students. Therefore, there is a need for systematic teacher training programs on inclusion and future workforce education. This should allow teachers to experience the consequences of the

education they are trying to provide for their students and ensure that it is incorporated into their teaching practice.

Table 2 shows basic teacher training programs designed to make this possible. In Korea, more than 14,000 teachers have been trained through in-service training programs over the past 15 years. By region, the Seoul Research Association, Incheon Research Association, Gyeonggi Research Association, Gangwon Research Association, Chungnam Daejeon Research Association, Jeonbuk Research Association, Daegu Research Association, Gyeongnam Research Association, and Busan Research Association have been formed, and many studies have been conducted in educational settings.

Table 2. Teacher Training Basic Training Program for Receptivity Training.

№	Title	Details
1	Principles 1	Understanding the Overall Content and Declaring the Ultimate Goal
2	Principles 2	Concept of the Five Elements and Their Organic Interrelationship
3	DQ (Cognitive Intelligence Quotient)	Assessment of Reading Ability and Current Reading Proficiency
4	Principles of Intellectual Power / 5-Dimensional Reading Method	The Nine-Stage Principle of Academic Information Processing and Proper Reading Methods
5	Speed Literacy (Comprehension) Reading Method 1	Practical Training in Speed Literacy Reading Method to Increase Information Volume
6	Speed Literacy (Comprehension) Reading Method 2	Transition from Speed Reading to Effective Learning Methods
7	Language Learning Method	Application of the Core Principle and Five Sub-Principles in English Utilization
8	Principles of Mental Power	Principles of Mental Strength to Internalize Acquired True Knowledge
9	Responsiveness and 3-Minute Meditation	Three-Minute Meditation Practice to Strengthen Thinking Ability and Responsibility

10	Mental Power and Artistic Activities	Artistic Activities to Maximize Emotional Strength and Creativity
11	Principles of Physical Power	Principles for Proper Use of One's Body
12	Exercise Practice	Physical Condition Assessment and Training for Physical Strength Management
13	Self-Management Ability	Practical Principles for Execution Beyond Simple Planning
14	Principles of Time Management Method	Finding Fragmented Time, Prioritization, and High-Level Perspective Training
15	Balanced Energy Distribution Ability	Principles of Distributing Resources Such as Wealth, Time, Language, and Information Effectively
16	Principles of Human Relational Ability	Viewing Humans from Multiple Perspectives and Principles of a People-Centered Life
17	Strengths and Weaknesses Transformation Method	Experiential Practice in Strengths and Weaknesses Transformation of Family Members and Recognizing Their Value
18	Finding Personal Traits	Self-Discovery Practice to Overcome Feelings of Superiority and Inferiority
19	Mission Statement	Writing a Personal Mission Statement Aligned with One's Unique Traits
20	DQ Index and Five-Element Development Method	Comprehensive Analysis of DQ Index Results and Individual Self-Perception with Practical Training for Developing the Five Elements
21	Life High-Altitude Perspective	Principles and Practical Training for Achieving a High-Level Life Goal
22	Integrated Lesson Model	Integrated Lesson Model for Comprehensive Application of the Five Elements and Skill Enhancement

23	Self-Directed Learning Model	Practical Training in Learning Models That Maximize Knowledge Utilization
24	Content-Based Teaching Methods	Structured Explanation of Content Systems Based on Verified Data and Results
25	Group Discussion and Presentation	Group Discussion on Learning Plans and Presentation of Transformation Cases

Training for parents

Before you can educate your children well, you need to put in place a parental education program that addresses their issues. Instead of teaching children how to succeed by beating others, we should teach them how to live life right. We must overcome the materialism, greedy egoism, and fictitious success that eat away at our children. To do this, we must help them maximize their talents by gradually strengthening their intellect, mental, physical strength, self-management, and relationship abilities. Table 3 shows a basic receptivity education program that has been taught to more than 5,000 people through parent education trainings in Korea over the past 15 years.

Table 3. Parents Training Basic Training Program for Receptivity Training.

№	Topic	Training Content
1	Principles of Receptive Education & Mental Strength	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ① The Only Life – How to Win ② The Right Learning System ③ The Three Principles of Talent Maximization ④ Meditation Techniques to Strengthen the Mind
2	Physical Strength & Intellectual Strength (Speed Comprehension Reading Method)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ① Two Core Principles of Health ② Methods for Correcting Body Structure ③ Understanding My Information Processing Ability ④ Increasing Information Volume – Speed Comprehension Reading Method
3	Human Relational Ability (Strengths and Weaknesses Transformation Method)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ① Basic Concepts of Human Relationships ② Fundamental Principles of Human Relationships ③ Viewing Humans from Multiple Perspectives ④ Transforming Weaknesses into Strengths
4	Self-Management Ability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ① Understanding My Time Management Ability ② Increasing the Quantity of Time ③ Enhancing the Quality of Time

6. Success Story of Inclusive Education in Kazakhstan through Five Dimensional Education

1) Inclusive education through Five Dimensional Education

The following is an example of the implementation of Five Dimensional Education at the Almaty Dia Global Academy, founded in 2015.

The situation of students at Dia Global Academy in Almaty

Students with IQs measured below 75 are required to receive special education. However, it has been proven that students with disabilities and other challenges can be taught together, and that they actually improve their relationships, creativity, and problem-solving skills, just like their non-disabled peers.

At Dia Global Academy, children with disabilities and challenges such as ADHD, autism, learning disabilities, expelled students, school maladjustment, and physical disabilities (such as polio) are placed in general education classes in proportions that are appropriate for each class.

Table 4. Results of the students after nine months of five-dimensional education. (Expelled from General Schools) Over 9 Months (September 2023 – May 2024).

Имя/Класс	Предмет (Креативное мышление)	Результат при поступлении (уровень 2 класса)	Результат по окончании обучения (согласно своей возрастной категории)	
Чернояров Даниил 6 класс	Чтение	Скорость/мин	147	250
		Понимание	10%	100%
Айманшин Темирлан 8 класс	Чтение	Скорость/мин	111	198
		Понимание	40%	100%
Агуреев Артем 8 класс	Чтение	Скорость/мин	140	408
		Понимание	50%	100%
Гомартели Артем 7 класс	Чтение	Скорость/мин	47	100
		Понимание	15%	100%
Зубков Вадим 8 класс	Чтение	Скорость/мин	77	128
		Понимание	30%	90%
Шек Дмитрий 8 класс	Чтение	Скорость/мин	62	160
		Понимание	10%	100%
Телемтаев Ринат 5 класс	Чтение	Скорость/мин	77	150
		Понимание	60%	100%

We can't give you every example, so here's the most recent one.

In September 2024, we conducted a 9-month 5D frontal training for 7 school expelled students.

The students were in grades 5, 6, 7, and 8.

Their intellect was tested in reading and math at the start of the program, and their ability to comprehend text in reading was below the third grade level. (See Table 4)

Mood was suicidal or very negative and angry.

Physical fitness was good in terms of health, but very far from the goal of being able to do the tasks that the 5th Dimension Education aims for.

Self-management skills were also very low in terms of time, language, and attitude management.

Self-understanding of interpersonal skills, metacognition of friendship with parents and teachers was not healthy, and they often quarreled.

After nine months of Fifth Dimension training, miraculously, they all returned to school and were called "troublemakers" in their previous schools, but now they are called honor students, talented children, and model students. Most of all, it is rewarding to see the changes in the children themselves and hear them confess that this was the most important year of their lives.

The following table (Table 4) shows the results of the students after nine months of five-dimensional education. Only the creative intelligence (reading) test is recorded in this table. Better information acquisition leads to better comprehension in all subjects, which leads to better grades. In fact, they go back to school and get good grades.

Recently, it has become a celebration because for the third year in a row, ordinary, even at first a little behind, children graduated from the Diaglobal preschool, went to school, participated in the Math Olympiad and took the first and second places in all of Almaty. (Fig. 13, 14, 15, 16)

Figure 13, 14, 15, 16. Diplomas and Certificates from Olympiads.

1) The significance of the success of inclusive education in Kazakhstan with the Five Dimensions of Education

First, methods from developed countries have produced record-breaking results in Central Asia.

Existing good methods were only working for a small percentage of children in Central Asia.

Second, inclusive education has been achieved by including both typical children and children with disabilities.

Third, teacher education and parent education are being successfully conducted, and the cooperation between education and home is having a positive impact on children.

Fourth, as a result of education, there is a clear improvement in grades and changes in character.

Fifth, it has resulted in the inclusion and integration of a society that has been discriminated against and segregated by people with and without disabilities.

We don't base our selection of children on how smart they are. It doesn't matter if they have a disability or are currently underachieving. What matters is that the parents are with us in our education.

Conclusion

Five-Dimensional Education is not abstract. It is already systematically structured with 25 curricula, and students can learn step by step by following the textbooks according to their level. Of course, the teacher's teaching method is crucial. Teachers should first experience and practice the curriculum themselves so they can understand the students' perspectives and provide better guidance. Equally important is parent education. Over the past 10 years of training parents, we have seen a transformation in their perception of education, themselves, and society. By combining a structured curriculum, teacher training, and parent education, inclusive education can become a reality.

We highly applaud Uzbekistan's initiative to implement inclusive education and propose Five Dimensional Education for successful inclusive education.

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